

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Stress level and stress management ability among the professionals of information technology in Chennai

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Abstract

Stress level and Stress management is a current issue faced by information technology (IT) professionals. In this condition, information technology (IT) professionals handle their stress level and stress management level through the emotional and intellectual commitment to a group or organization that results in conduct that will assist a company in keeping its promises to improve the workers and, in turn, business outcomes. Information technology (IT) is currently dealing with new difficulties and problems relating to employee stress level and stress management level. The software industry has a high-stress level because of the nature of the work, the goals, the successes, the night shift, and the excessive workload. However, stress frequently has a negative connotation, and this part of stress is referred to as distress. Therefore, in front of other issues, the stress level and stress management level will be playing a major role in information technology (IT) companies. For this study, the researcher determines the stress level and stress management level ability among information technology (IT) professionals. A few information technology (IT) experts in Chennai were surveyed to use a standardized questionnaire to get the primary data. Materials from primary sources, such as books, journals, articles, newspapers, etc., were used to assess secondary data. The research provides valuable insights for the companies to understand the relationship between stress level and stress management and how this level of stress management will affect the employees.

Keywords: Employee Stress Level; Information Technology (IT); Human Resource Management (HRM); Employee Stress Management

1. Introduction

Information technology (IT) is a branch of business that focuses on corporate software operations, computer network and database administration, and information security. Information technology (IT) is now dealing with several new problems and challenges due to various factors, including expanding the internet, improved processing power, modern operating systems, increased online security, wireless and mobile communication protocol systems, etc. Information technology (IT) organizations are responsible for ensuring that operations function smoothly. They guarantee that gadgets are functioning correctly and that data is protected. Information technology (IT) is also in charge of installing new software and hardware as well as providing technical assistance. The two primary categories of employers in the Information technology (IT) industry are those who use the technology and those who create or build software.

Stress is the strain on our bodies and minds brought on by how we react to pressure from the outside environment. It is meant to increase stress levels. Stress management is described as the tools, tactics, or procedures used to alleviate stress and the adverse effects it has on mental or physical well-being. To handle stress, a variety of approaches can be utilized. These include mental, emotional, and behavioral methods. Because it enables workers to handle the demands

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of their jobs and have an excellent work-life balance, stress management is vital in work-life. Employees who are under stress may exhibit symptoms of anxiety, sadness, impatience, and trouble concentrating.

The present study aims to examine the Socio-Economic profile of information technology (IT) professionals and to identify the stress level and stress management level among the respondents of information technology (IT) professionals.

2. Methodology

As it explains the traits of individuals or groups, the current study is descriptive in nature. The researchers have used both primary and secondary data for this study. The core information was gathered directly from the information technology (IT) running a company in Chennai. The secondary data were gathered via the Internet, publications, journals, etc. The researchers used a structured questionnaire to gather primary data from respondents. A tiny group of information technology specialists were given access to the structured questionnaire, and minor adjustments were made in response to their feedback.

The objective of the study is to identify the ability of stress level and stress management among the respondents of information technology (IT) professionals. Thus, Information technology (IT) professionals from various Chennai locations were chosen as the study's samples by convincing sampling. The researchers distributed the structural questionnaire to 105 information technology (IT) experts. The overall sample size for the current study is 105 respondents since 105 people completed the entire structural questionnaire. Tools of stress management index analysis and per centage analysis are used.

3. Result and discussion

This study focuses on respondents with the professions, testers, project managers, network operations, finance, years of experience, technical writers, administration, software developers, HR's, business analysts, and others.

3.1. Socio economic profile

This study focuses on the socio-economic profile of respondents, marital status, gender, taking care of children, age, education status, and no. Children, average monthly income, no.of. Members in the family and no.of. Employed members of the family.

Table 1 Socio economic profile

S.NO	Categories	Respondent		Per centage
1	Age	Above 45 years	20	19.05
		30-45 years	34	32.38
		Less than 30 years	51	48.57
2	Gender	Female	49	46.67
		Male	55	52.38
		Prefer not to say	1	0.95
3	Marital status	Unmarried	55	52.38
		Married	50	47.62
4	No. of. children	More than 3	4	3.81
		3	3	2.86
		2	34	32.38
		1	13	12.38
		0	51	48.57

5	Take care of children	Crèche/daycare	51	48.57
		Housemaid	7	6.67
		Parents	22	20.95
		In-laws	15	14.29
		Spouse	10	9.52
6	Education status	Postgraduate	83	79.04
		Undergraduate	19	18.09
		Others	3	2.87
7	No. of. members in the family	Above 5	32	30.48
		4	46	43.81
		3	21	20
		2	6	5.71
8	No. of. employed members in the family	Above 5	2	1.9
		3 - 4	43	40.96
		Up to 2	60	57.14
9	Average monthly income	More than 1,00,000	6	5.72
		Less than 1,00,000	30	28.57
		Less than 50,000	42	40
		Less than 25,000	13	12.38
		Less than 15,000	14	13.33
10	Years of experience	More than 10 Years	26	24.76
		5 - 10 years	39	37.14
		Less than 5 years	40	38.1
11	Working days per week	7 days	5	4.76
		6 days	87	82.86
		5 days	11	10.48
		Less than 5 days	2	1.9

Source: Primary Data.

The socioeconomic position of the respondents is shown in the table, which shows that 52.38 per cent of respondents are men and 46.67 per cent of respondents are women. Majority A total of 48.57 per cent of responders are under 30 years old. The age group of 30-45 years accounts for 32.38 per cent of respondents, while the remaining 19.05 per cent of respondents are in the age group. It is obvious that most responders are single if they are above 45. The per centage of employees who are married is 47.62 per cent, followed by 52.38 per cent of those who are single. The majority 48.57 per cent of respondents say they have no children, 32.38 per cent say they have two children, 12.38 per cent say they have one kid, more than three children are in the family, according to 3.81 per cent of respondents, while three children are in the family for 2.86 per cent of respondents. In their household, the majority of respondents (48.57 per cent) work as a daycare provider, followed by parents (20.95 per cent), in-laws (14.29 per cent), spouse (9.52 per cent), and housemaid (6.67 per cent). 79.04 per cent of respondents completed postgraduate work, 18.09 per cent of respondents finished undergraduate work, and 2.87 per cent of respondents finished other types of coursework. A whopping 43.81 per cent of respondents have four family members, followed by 30.48 per cent who have five or more, 20 per cent who

have three, and 5.71 per cent who have only two, 57.14 per cent of respondents are aged between one and two, 40.96 per cent are aged between three and four, and 1.90 per cent are aged five or more. Thirty-four per cent of respondents have monthly incomes of less than rupees 15,000, 12.38 per cent of respondents earn less than rupees 25,000, 40 per cent of respondents earn less than rupees 50,000, 28.57 per cent of respondents earn less than rupees 100,000, and 13.44 per cent of respondents earn less than rupees 15,000. With five to ten years of experience, 37.14 per cent of the workforce. With more than ten years of experience, 24.76 per cent of the workforce. Six days a week is the maximum number of days that 82.86 per cent of respondents work.

3.2. Stress level among information technology (IT) employee

Stress management plays a vital role in the success of an individual. Many recent researches prove that a person with a high-stress level is highly successful in life when compared with a low level of stress management. Five key elements make up stress management: self-awareness, self-regulations, self-motivation, social awareness, and social abilities. It is also proved that employee with high stress management level is highly successful in their job. The top-rated employee's stress management scores are high. Thus, to determine the level of stress management among Chennai employees. The stress level Index was designed to determine the level of stress management among employees.

Table 2 Stress level among information technology (it) employee

S.NO	Stress Level	Respondent	Per centage
1	Less than 20	NIL	00
2	21 – 40	NIL	00
3	41 – 60	32	30.48
4	61 – 80	69	65.71
5	81 and above	4	3.81

Source: Primary Data.

Table 2 reveals that the level of stress management was classified into five groups like Less than 20, 21 to 40, 41 to 60, 61 to 80, and 81 and above. By applying the formula for calculating the stress management level using the Stress Management Index, it concluded that the majority, 65.71 per cent, of the employees have a high level of stress management. Only nearly 30.48 per cent of the employees have an average stress management level, i.e., 41 to 60 and 3.81 per cent of the employees have a low level of stress management, i.e., 81 and above. None of the employees have a low level of stress management. This proves the previous research to be valid. As an employee, one should have a high level of stress management. To be more successful, the level of stress management should also be increased among the employees.

The majority, 65.71 per cent, of the employees are having a high level of stress. Only nearly 30.48 per cent of the employees have an average stress level, i.e., 41 to 60 and 3.81 per cent of the employees have a low level of stress, i.e., 81 and above.

Table 3 Stress management level among information technology (it) employee

S.NO	Stress Management	Respondent	Per centage
1	Less than 20	Nil	00
2	21 – 40	1	0.95
3	41 – 60	16	15.24
4	61 – 80	83	79.05
5	81 and above	5	4.76

Source: Primary Data.

Table 3 reveals that the level of stress management was classified into five groups like Less than 20, 21 to 40, 41 to 60, 61 to 80, and 81 & and above. By applying the formula for calculating the stress management level using the Stress Management Index, it concluded that the majority, 79.05 per cent, of the employees have a high level of stress

management. Only 15.24 per cent and 4.76 per cent of the employees have an average stress management level, i.e., 41 to 60 and 81 and above. 0.95 per cent of employees have a low level of stress management, 21 to 40. This proves the previous research to be valid. As an employee, one should have a high level of stress management. To be more successful, the level of stress management should also be increased among the employees.

The majority, 79.05 per cent, of the employees have a high level of stress management. Only 15.24 per cent and 4.76 per cent of the employees have an average stress management level.

4. Conclusion

This study concluded that the majority of the information technology (IT) professionals in Chennai have a high level of Stress level and Stress management. Only a tiny section of the employees has an average Stress level and Stress management. Many researches have proved that successful employees have a high level of stress level and stress management. This study also reveals that information technology (IT) professionals have a high level of stress level and stress management, which also indicates their successful in their company. Less than 10 per cent of information technology (IT) professionals have an average stress level and stress management. If proper training and development activities related to stress level and stress management are carried out, the employees can also be successful in their career it can be concluded that when age increases, the stress level and stress management also increase. This states that when the employees are financially sound it influences the level of stress level and stress management.

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